

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A new nomenclature for the livestock-associated *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex based on phylogenomics

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

Michaela Zwyer^{1,2}, Cengiz Çavusoglu ⁴,
 Maria Lodovica Pacciarini⁵, Erika Scaltriti⁶, Dick Van Soolingen^{7,8}, Anna Dötsch^{1,2},
 Miriam Reinhard^{1,2}, Sebastien Gagneux ^{1,2}

¹Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute, Basel, Switzerland

²University of Basel, Basel, Switzerland

³Department of Medical Microbiology, Ege University Faculty of Medicine, Izmir, Turkey

⁴Institute for Food Safety and Hygiene, University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

⁵National Reference Centre for Bovine Tuberculosis, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e dell'Emilia Romagna, Brescia, Italy

⁶Risk Analysis and Genomic Epidemiology Unit, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e dell'Emilia-Romagna, Parma, Italy

⁷National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), Bilthoven, Netherlands Antilles

⁸Department of Medical Microbiology, Radboud University Nijmegen Medical Centre, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

V1 First published: 25 Aug 2021, 1:100
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14029.1>
 Latest published: 01 Dec 2021, 1:100
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14029.2>

Abstract

Background

The bacteria that compose the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC) cause tuberculosis (TB) in humans and in different animals, including livestock. Much progress has been made in understanding the population structure of the human-adapted members of the MTBC by combining phylogenetics with genomics. Accompanying the discovery of new genetic diversity, a body of operational nomenclature has evolved to assist comparative and molecular epidemiological studies of human TB. By contrast, for the livestock-associated MTBC members, *Mycobacterium bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*, there has been a lack of comprehensive nomenclature to accommodate new genetic diversity uncovered by emerging phylogenomic studies. We propose to fill this gap by putting forward a new nomenclature covering the main phylogenetic groups within *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*.

Methods

We gathered a total of 8,747 whole-genome sequences (WGS) from public sources and 39 newly sequenced strains, and selected a subset of 839 WGS, representative of the worldwide diversity of *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*. We used phylogenetics and genetic diversity patterns inferred from WGS to define groups.

Open Peer Review

Reviewer Status ? ?

Invited Reviewers

1 2

version 2

(revision)
01 Dec 2021

version 1

25 Aug 2021

?

report

?

report

1. **Lorraine Michelet**, Paris-Est University, Marne-la-Vallée, France

2. **Liliana C. M. Salvador** , University of Georgia, Athens, USA

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Results

We propose to divide *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*, in three main phylogenetic lineages, which we named La1, La2 and La3, respectively. Within La1, we identified several monophyletic groups, which we propose to classify into eight sublineages (La1.1-La1.8). These differed in geographic distribution, with some being geographically restricted and others globally widespread, suggesting different expansion abilities. To ease molecular characterization of these MTBC groups by the community, we provide phylogenetically informed, single nucleotide polymorphisms that can be used as barcodes for genotyping. These makers were implemented in a new test suit in KvarQ, a platform-independent, open-source tool.

Conclusions

Our results contribute to an improved classification of the genetic diversity within the livestock-associated MTBC, which will benefit future molecular epidemiological and evolutionary studies.

Keywords

zoonotic tuberculosis, genetic diversity, mycobacterium tuberculosis complex, phylogenetics, whole-genome sequencing

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Corresponding author: Daniela Brites (d.brites@swisstop.ch)

Author roles: **Zwyer M:** Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Çavusoglu C:** Resources, Writing – Review & Editing; **Ghielmetti G:** Resources, Writing – Review & Editing; **Pacciarini ML:** Resources, Writing – Review & Editing; **Scaltriti E:** Resources, Writing – Review & Editing; **Van Soolingen D:** Resources, Writing – Review & Editing; **Dötsch A:** Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Reinhard M:** Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Gagneux S:** Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Project Administration, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Brites D:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No ECOEVODRTB_883582) This work was also supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation (CRSII5_177163 and 310030_188888)

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

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How to cite this article: Zwyer M, Çavusoglu C, Ghielmetti G *et al.* **A new nomenclature for the livestock-associated *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex based on phylogenomics [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2021, 1:100 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14029.1>

First published: 25 Aug 2021, 1:100 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14029.1>

Plain language summary

Tuberculosis affects humans and livestock species. Its etiological agents are different bacteria belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC). In recent years, whole-genome sequencing (WGS) has become essential in both basic and clinical tuberculosis research. Based on WGS, different human-adapted MTBC genotypes have been classified into lineages and sublineages, which have been shown to differ in their geographic distribution and in virulence. Studies based on WGS are starting to emerge also for livestock-associated MTBC pathogens, but a body of operational nomenclature systematically covering all known genetic diversity is missing. After gathering several thousands of WGS, we propose here a backbone of operational nomenclature to classify the genetic diversity uncovered by genomic studies of livestock-associated MTBC. Furthermore, a set of molecular markers were provided which can be used to identify the newly proposed lineages and sublineages.

Introduction

Tuberculosis is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in humans¹, and bovine TB (bTB), remains a major economic problem and continues to be a zoonotic threat in many places around the world^{2,3}. Human TB is caused mostly by members of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC), collectively known as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, and *M. africanum*, whereas bTB in livestock is primarily caused by *M. bovis*. These organisms, and the other members of the MTBC⁴, share more than 99% identical nucleotide sequences but can vary considerably in gene content⁵. The MTBC comprises several unique phylogenetic lineages that differ mostly by chromosomal deletions and point mutations. No significant homologous recombination between strains or gene insertion via horizontal gene transfer occurs in the MTBC⁶⁻⁸. Despite their high genetic similarity and strict clonality, these lineages exhibit striking differences in host tropism, infecting a wide range of mammalian hosts⁹. For the human-adapted MTBC, a good understanding of the population structure has emerged through comparative analyses of whole-genome sequences (WGS) of TB patient isolates from all over the world. The human-adapted MTBC can be classified into nine phylogenetic lineages: Lineage 1 (L1) to L7, and more recently, two new lineages, L8¹⁰ and L9¹¹, have been described but remain poorly characterized. Lineages 1-4 and L7 correspond collectively to *Mycobacterium tuberculosis sensu stricto*, whereas L5 and L6 are traditionally known as *M. africanum*. Further subdivisions among the human-adapted MTBC lineages have been proposed by many different studies to highlight existing within-lineage differences in geographic distribution and genetic differentiation. By contrast, the animal-adapted members of the MTBC remain much less characterized, and are typically named according to the host species from which they were first, or most commonly, isolated. Considering the growing number of WGS available for many of these pathogens, a more comprehensive and systematic nomenclature beyond the species name is necessary for assisting comparative and molecular epidemiology studies. This situation is particularly pressing in the case of *M. bovis*, for which there are currently

thousands of WGS in the public domain. We and others, have previously gathered several thousands WGS of *M. bovis*, generating initial insights into the world-wide population structure of this pathogen based on complete genomes¹²⁻¹⁵. Through these efforts, several *M. bovis* sub-populations have been identified, and while some corresponded to previously identified *M. bovis* clonal complexes known to be important causes of bTB world-wide¹⁶⁻¹⁹, several others remained unclassified¹²⁻¹⁵. Here, we fill this gap, and propose a comprehensive nomenclature, based on phylogenetic principles and genetic diversity patterns, for the main groups found in what is currently known as *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*.

The nomenclature used for the different members of the MTBC has been repeatedly revised over time, with a particular focus on whether the different MTBC members should be considered separated species or the same species given their high genomic similarity²⁰. Classifying the different MTBC members into ecotypes has also been proposed, to better accommodate the differences in host range of the different MTBC members^{21,22}. The nomenclature we propose here is not intended as a replacement but rather to serve as an operational nomenclature to assist genomic comparative studies. We propose to take the same hierarchical levels of classification as has been adopted for the human-adapted MTBC lineages and sublineages, as it has proven to be robust and flexible enough to capture diversity both at a global and local level, and is also adequate to describe newly discovered diversity (e.g. L9 and L8). Given the difficulties in defining populations in bacteria, we would like to emphasize that the nomenclature proposed here, might, but does not necessarily have to reflect cohesive groups sharing biological properties. It is rather a pragmatic attempt to find a classification that will usefully describe the genetic diversity and the phylogeographic patterns observed in the MTBC affecting livestock.

Methods

Data collection

Representative dataset for livestock-associated MTBC. We searched the US National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) for new publicly available WGS of *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*, using names as search terms: for example for *M. bovis*, “*Mycobacterium tuberculosis variant bovis* [organism]” was searched. Our search was restricted to the time period between the 11th of March 2019, when we already had gathered 3,364 WGS¹², until the 4th of November 2020. A total of 5,383 new genomes concordant with our search terms were available. From these genomes, we excluded those that met the following criteria prior to analysis: genomes registered as bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG), as laboratory strains, with unknown country of isolation or isolated in countries already over-represented in previous analyses (Mexico, USA, UK, New Zealand)¹², and genomes corresponding to strains isolated in patients from low endemic countries with unknown country of origin. Genomes that were publicly available but unpublished at the time of WGS retrieval, were also excluded after a preliminary analysis, as they did not provide new main phylogenetic clades once compared to the representative

set of genomes of *M. bovis* and *M. caprae* previously published¹². Finally, WGS that did not meet our criteria for downstream analysis (average whole-genome coverage > 15x and ratio of heterogenous SNPs to fixed SNPs < 1) were excluded. Furthermore, we newly sequenced 19 genomes from Turkey isolated from humans, two genomes from Italy isolated in cattle in Apulia and Sicily²³, and four genomes from Switzerland isolated in cattle²⁴. The selected genomes were added to a previous reference set representing the world-wide diversity of *M. bovis* (n=464) and *M. caprae* (n=12) selected after an initial compilation of 3,364 WGS¹². For *M. orygis*, 14 newly sequenced genomes isolated from patients and from different zoo animals of South Asian origin²⁵ were obtained and analysed together with 77 publicly available WGS (*Extended data*, Table 1). In total, 839 representative genomes were considered, of which 685 were *M. bovis*, 63 *M. caprae*, and 91 *M. orygis*. With respect to our previous representative dataset¹², 221 new genomes were added to the downstream analysis for *M. bovis* (*Extended data*, Table 1). Most of these were from animal strains isolated in Brazil (n=19), France (n=93), Germany (n=40), Ethiopia (n=37) and Mali (n=3)^{13-15,26,27}, while few derived from human isolates from Tanzania (n=1), Indonesia (n=1), Kazakhstan (n=2) and Moldova (n=1)²⁸⁻³⁰ (*Extended data*, Table 1). In the case of *M. caprae*, 51 genomes isolated from Spain were added³¹. The 39 newly sequenced genomes were uploaded to EBI under the study accession numbers PRJEB46653 and PRJEB46575 (*Extended data*, Table 1).

Representative dataset for the complete MTBC. In order to obtain a representative set of world-wide sampled MTBC genomes from both animal and human isolates with a discernible tree topology, we randomly selected genomes from a large in-house collection of WGS (approximately 50,000), for the human lineages 1-6 and for *M. bovis*. The genomes were selected according to the following scheme: 50 random genomes per continent (Africa, America, Asia, Europe, and Oceania) for each lineage. For lineage 1-6, genomes isolated in Northern America, Europe (except Eastern Europe), and Oceania were required to have information about the country of birth of the patient to be considered. Furthermore, WGS from the following strains were added: three strains belonging to the proto Beijing sublineage, eight pyrazinamide susceptible *M. bovis* strains¹², five L9 strains, 27 L7 strains, two L8 strains, 57 *M. caprae* strains, 15 *M. microti* strains, 84 *M. orygis* strains, six *M. pinnipedii* strains, two ancient genomes from Peruvian mummies, one each of Chimp and Dassie bacillus, and one each of *M. mungi* and *M. suricattae*. A complete list containing the accession numbers of all genomes included (n=1226) can be found in the supplementary data (*Extended data*, Table 2).

Bacterial culture, DNA extraction and whole-genome sequencing

The MTBC isolates were grown in 7H9-Tween 0.05% medium (BD) +/- 40mM sodium pyruvate. We extracted genomic DNA after harvesting the bacterial cultures in the late exponential phase of growth using the CTAB method³². Sequencing libraries were prepared using NEXTERA XT DNA and

the EBNext Ultra II DNA Library Preparation Kits (Illumina, San Diego, USA). Multiplexed libraries were paired-end and single-end sequenced using Illumina HiSeq 2500 (Illumina, San Diego, USA), Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) and MiSeq (Illumina, San Diego, USA) with 151, 101 and 250 cycles, respectively.

Bioinformatic analysis

Whole-genome sequence analysis. All WGS downloaded, as well as those generated in-house, were analyzed using the WGS analysis pipeline described in 33. Briefly, the retrieved FASTQ files were processed with *Trimmomatic* v0.33³⁴ to remove the Illumina adaptors and to trim low quality reads. Only reads of at least 20 bp were kept for further analysis. *SeqPrep* v 1.2 was then used to merge overlapping paired-end reads (overlap size = 15). We then mapped the resulting reads to the reconstructed ancestral sequence of the MTBC³⁵ using *BWA* v0.7.13³⁶ (mem algorithm). Duplicated reads were marked by the Mark Duplicates module of *Picard* v 2.9.1 and then excluded. We further performed local realignment of reads around INDELS using the *RealignerTargetCreator* and *IndelRealigner* modules of *GATK* v 3.4.0³⁷. *Samtools* v1.2 *mpileup*³⁸ and *VarScan* v2.4.1³⁹ were then used for SNP calling with the subsequent thresholds: minimum mapping quality of 20, minimum base quality at a position of 20, minimum read depth at a position of 7x and maximum strand bias of 90%. Only SNPs with a frequency of $\geq 90\%$ within an isolate were considered, and for those with a frequency of $\leq 10\%$ the ancestor state was called. The *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv reference annotation (NC_000962.3, NCBI) was used as the genome of *M. bovis* (AF2122/97, NCBI) has no genes absent from H37Rv, except for *TbD1*⁴⁰. SNPs were annotated with *SnEff* v4.11⁴¹. Positions falling in PE/PPE genes, phages, insertion sequences, and in regions with at least 50 bp identity to other genomic regions were excluded⁴².

In silico spoligotyping. All WGS were *in silico* spoligotyped using *KvarQ*⁴³. The respective SB numbers were retrieved by entering the spoligotype patterns into the *Mycobacterium bovis* Spoligotype Database and are reported in *Extended data*, Table 1.

Phylogenetic analyses. The phylogenetic trees were constructed from alignments of variable positions with a percentage of missing data of $\leq 10\%$. With *RAXML* v 8.2.11⁴⁴ maximum-likelihood phylogenies were constructed by using the general time-reversible model of sequence evolution (-m GTRCAT -V), a rapid bootstrap analysis with 1000 bootstraps and search for the best-scoring maximum-likelihood phylogeny. The MTBC phylogeny was rooted with *M. canetti* (SAMN00102920, NCBI) while all other phylogenies were rooted with a lineage 6 strain (SAMEA3359865, NCBI). Phylogenetic trees were plotted with *ggtree*⁴⁵ and *Figtree*.

Population structure and genetic distances. Population structure was evaluated using a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) based on all polymorphic positions obtained from the 1,226 dataset, using the R package *adegenet*⁴⁶ in R 3.5.2.

Between and within group genetic distances were measured as raw pair-wise SNP differences for the different groups using the R package *ape*⁴⁷.

Maps of geographic distribution. The geographical origin of the isolates and host-related metadata were recovered from NCBI and used to inform geographic ranges. Strains isolated from zoo animals or isolated from humans living in Europe, Oceania, or North America with unknown place of birth were not taken into account. Since WGS is not performed on a regular basis in all countries, relying only on WGS data would underestimate the geographical distribution of certain clades. To adjust for that, we used the *in silico* SB numbers shown to be phylogenetically informative¹², and searched for publications reporting those SB numbers and their associated geography (*Extended data*, Table 3). The countries of isolation identified in this way were added to those obtained from the WGS and were used to obtain geographic distributions using the *rworldmap* package⁴⁸ in R 3.5.2⁴⁹.

Validation of lineage- and sublineage- specific markers. In order to obtain a list of polymorphic positions specific to all members of a defined lineage or sublineage, the variant calls obtained from the 839 La1, La2, and La3 WGS were merged using *BCFtools*. On the merged dataset, the following filtering steps were applied: First only positions mutated in at least seven genomes were kept using *VCftools* (--mac 7)⁵⁰, second only positions with a FILTER flag PASS were kept using *BCFtools*. The first filtering step was included, since we were only interested in SNPs that are common to all members of a sublineage and the lowest number of WGS for a sublineage was seven (unknown6). A genotype matrix was created using the R package *VariantAnnotation*⁵¹ and by using customized python scripts, those variants mutated in all members of a specific lineage or sublineage, or in a monophyletic group of multiple sublineages (e.g. La1.3 and La1.2) were extracted. This resulted in a list containing 2,203 variants specific to 19 different sublineages and combinations of multiple sublineages. Additionally, we created a list of polymorphic positions using 4,742 WGS representing the genetic diversity of human-adapted lineages L1-L7 and L9³³ and to ensure that our SNPs defining lineages and sublineages among livestock-associated MTBC were specific, we excluded all positions that were polymorphic in the set of 4,742 genomes. This way, a final list of 1,959 SNPs specific to a lineage, sublineage or sublineage combinations within livestock-associated MTBC, and not polymorphic in any of human-adapted MTBC lineages, was achieved (*Extended data*, Table 4). Out of the 1,959 SNPs, 87 (three to five variants per lineage and sublineage or sublineage combinations) were selected to create a new *test suite* specific for the livestock-associated MTBC in *KvarQ*⁴³. In order to validate the specificity of the 87 SNPs used in the new *KvarQ* test suite, we scanned 2,861 livestock-associated WGS from 12 that were not included in the 839 dataset, and 66 additional WGS randomly chosen from recent publications⁵²⁻⁵⁴ (*Extended data*, Table 5). The 2,927 fastq files were also processed using the workflow described in the WGS sequence analysis section and a phylogenetic tree was inferred as

described above. The phylogenetic tree was compared to the lineage and sublineage identity as determined by *KvarQ*, to assess the accuracy and specificity of the test suite.

Results and Discussion

Classification of livestock-associated MTBC into new lineages

After screening an extensive collection of approximately 50,000 WGS, we compiled a comprehensive set of 1,226 WGS representing all MTBC members from all continents in the world (except Antarctica). For the human-adapted lineages (L1 to L6) as well as for *M. bovis*, a large number of WGS is available, and in order to obtain an even representation of these groups with a discernable topology, 50 representatives were randomly selected from each continent and from each lineage. The phylogenetic relationships of these randomly selected 1,226 MTBC strains are represented in *Figure 1A*. The results indicated that the human-adapted MTBC members are paraphyletic, given that the group defined by the Region of Difference 9 (RD9)⁵⁵ comprises human (L6 and L9) and animal-adapted members (*Figure 1A*), in line with previous findings⁴. While the distinct clades of the human-adapted members were separated into different lineages and have been named accordingly (Lineage 1-9), the animal-adapted members are still only referred to by their species name. Recent studies, and our searches for WGS from the public domain, indicated that there is a wealth of WGS, in particular for *M. bovis*, representing different geographical areas, hosts, and epidemiological settings of the world^{12-15,26,27,56-58}. *M. orygis*, which has been recently suggested to be the main cause of zoonotic TB in South Asia and possibly a pathogen of cattle in that region⁵⁹, also has a growing number of genomes available. There is, however, a lack of consistent nomenclature to assist in the comparative analysis of these genomes. Therefore, we propose to adopt a lineage nomenclature that covers the main groups found in what is currently known as *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis* based on phylogenetics and genetic diversity patterns. For the remaining animal-adapted MTBC members, *M. mungi*, *M. suricattae*, the Dassie and Chimpanzee bacillus, as well as *M. pinnipedii* and *M. microti*, still too few WGS were available to allow for any meaningful within-lineage diversity analysis. In addition, the host range and ecology of these ecotypes remain poorly understood. We reasoned that these cases would require more extensive sampling, and thus focused the remaining of our analyses on *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*.

A phylogenomics-based nomenclature for *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*

These three members of the MTBC evolved from a common ancestor not shared by any other group within the MTBC (*Figure 1A*). The visual inspection of the phylogeny and the PCA plot suggested that among these three groups, there are four main phylogenetic clades: *M. orygis*, *M. caprae*, the pyrazinamide-susceptible *M. bovis*¹² and the pyrazinamide-resistant *M. bovis* (*Figure 1 A&B*). The long branches leading to these clades indicate that many genetic changes have occurred in their founding ancestor populations, and this was

Figure 1. A) Maximum Likelihood topology of 1,226 MTBC representatives, where 50 representatives were randomly selected from each continent and from each lineage (see methods). The tree was inferred from an alignment containing 103'841 polymorphic positions. Branch lengths are proportional to nucleotide substitutions. Support values correspond to bootstrap values. Members of the human-adapted MTBC have tips colored according to their lineage. **B)** Principal Component Analysis (PCA) derived from the same alignment as the phylogeny. The two first principal components are shown. **C)** Distribution of the raw pair-wise SNP distances between human adapted MTBC lineages and between different animal adapted MTBC members. **D)** Proposed lineage nomenclature for *M. bovis* susceptible and resistant to pyrazinamide, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*.

also reflected in the pair-wise SNP distances between these clades estimated from the 1,226 whole-genomes dataset (Figure 1C). We suggest classifying these four clades into three main lineages within the MTBC analogously to the human lineages, considering *M. bovis* pyrazinamide-resistant and -susceptible as one lineage, and *M. caprae* and *M. orygis* as two other main lineages. We propose adopting the numerical lineage nomenclature used for the human-adapted MTBC members, adding the lower-letter “a” standing for “animal”. This nomenclature distinguishes the human-adapted from the remaining members of the complex, which can be of relevance for clinicians; simultaneously, for the non-human adapted MTBC members, it has the advantage of being agnostic with respect to the host species, which can be multiple. In this way, we suggest naming La1, La2 and La3 the groups currently known as pyrazinamide-resistant and -susceptible *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*, respectively (Figure 1D).

The pyrazinamide-susceptible *M. bovis* group is composed of pyrazinamide-susceptible strains within *M. bovis*, and is geographically restricted to East Africa (Extended data, Table 1, Figure 2)¹². This group of strains were quite divergent from the pyrazinamide-resistant *M. bovis*, yet closer to the latter than to *M. caprae* (Figure 1C). A similar situation occurred within the human-adapted L2 when comparing the so-called Proto-Beijing group with the remaining strains of L2 (Figure 1C). The available WGS of pyrazinamide-susceptible *M. bovis* came from strains isolated in humans, cattle and a zoo antelope, and no new WGS in our current analysis have been added with respect to previous studies^{12,15}. *In silico* determination of spoligotypes (Extended data, Table 1) revealed that similar patterns are common in cattle from Tanzania and Uganda^{18,60,61}, and have also been observed in different wild animal species in Tanzania⁶¹. In our extensive WGS collections of MTBC isolates from TB patients in Uganda and Tanzania (unpublished), we did not find any representatives of pyrazinamide-susceptible *M. bovis*, suggesting that zoonotic transfers of this group of strains are rare, like for other *M. bovis* strains.

Unlike the human-adapted lineages of the MTBC, La1, La2 and La3 are multi-host pathogens known to infect livestock, other domestic and wild mammal species, and occasionally humans^{9,59}. The multiple host species from which these isolates were obtained, are in line with that notion (Extended data, Table 1). Despite this general broad host range, these

lineages differ substantially in their geographic distribution, suggesting local adaptation to different hosts and/or different dispersion abilities of their host populations (Figure 2). The evolutionary success of La1, and its broad distribution around the world, are linked with the ability of La1 to infect different species of livestock, in particular cattle. Additionally, its broad host tropism also contributes to this success, as demonstrated by the difficulties in eradicating bovine TB even in high-resource countries, where La1 can be maintained in different wildlife species that live in close proximity to livestock such as badgers, deer or wild boar⁶². Various molecular markers, and more recently WGS, suggest no preferential association of La1 genotypes with particular host species^{58,63,64}. It is thus still unclear whether La1 infections in non-bovid species are the result of spillover events from cattle populations (i.e. La1 is better adapted to cattle than to other animal species), or if La1 has an intrinsically broader host spectrum that can lead to similarly successful infectious cycles in many different animal species. Interestingly, despite its broad host repertoire and the ability to cause zoonotic TB, La1 is not able to sustainably cause infectious cycles in immune-competent humans. Despite being much less studied, a similar rationale might apply to La2 and La3, as we shall discuss next.

La2, or *M. caprae*, is globally associated with a much lower burden of disease compared to La1, and that is presumably also reflected in a much lower number of WGS available. La2 is, however, a significant regional cause of animal TB as it is the main cause of TB in goats in the Iberian Peninsula⁶⁵, affects several livestock and wild animal species populations in Central Europe^{66,67}, and is occasionally a source of zoonotic TB⁶⁸. Indeed, a study in Germany showed that up to one third of zoonotic TB cases in that country were caused by La2⁶⁹. Two of our newly sequenced genomes belonged to La2, with one corresponding to an isolate from cattle in Switzerland²⁴ and the other from a patient in Turkey (Figure 3). Both were closely related to La2 strains isolated in Spain and in Germany^{31,70}. The geographic distribution of La2 obtained from the WGS metadata and from searching the literature using the spoligotype patterns determined *in silico* (Extended data, Table 3) confirms, as previously suggested, that La2 is not restricted to Europe¹² but also occurs in Africa, South America and East Asia (Extended data, Table 1, Figure 2). Our phylogenetic reconstruction also revealed that La2 exhibits strong population divisions, in particular between isolates of Asian and European origin (Figure 1A & Figure 3). However, better sampling,

Figure 2. Geographic distribution of La1, La2 and La3 informed by WGS and *in silico* spoligotype patterns.

Figure 3. Maximum Likelihood topology based on 2,114 polymorphic positions derived from 91 WGS of La3, after conservatively filtering out several repetitive regions of the genome (see methods). Branch lengths are proportional to nucleotide substitutions and the topology is rooted with one L6 WGS. Support values correspond to bootstrap values. The different colors of the tips correspond to different hosts indicated in the legend. Country of isolation is indicated, followed by the country of birth in the case of human isolates, when known. Isolates with origin in South Asia are indicated in red. A cluster of WGS obtained from cattle isolated is indicated with A.

including more isolates from Africa, America and Asia, will be necessary to understand the biogeography and evolutionary history of La2.

The most distantly related group within the livestock-associated lineages is La3, commonly known as *M. orygis*. La3 was originally isolated from a captive *oryx* antelope, and has since then been isolated from many different wild, zoo and domestic animals, and from patients of South Asian origin in low endemic TB countries^{25,71–74}. In India, Bangladesh and Nepal, La3 has been isolated from humans, cattle, primates, deer and

a wild rhinoceros^{59,75,76}. The native geographic distribution of this pathogen seems to be restricted to South Asia where it is possibly the main cause of zoonotic TB⁵⁹. Here, we compiled 91 WGS of La3 from different sources: 1) isolates from low TB endemic countries from patients of South Asian (n=13) or unknown origin (n=35)⁷⁷, 2) isolates from patients in Southern India (n=5)⁵⁹ and one patient from Bangladesh⁷⁸, 3) isolates from cattle (n=15) and deer (n=5) from different Indian regions⁵⁹. The remaining publicly available genomes were of unknown origin and unknown host species. The 14 newly sequenced La3 isolates were obtained from zoo animals and from

patients of South Asian origin in the Netherlands²⁵ (*Extended data*, Table 1). The genetic relationships among the 91 WGS showed that the isolates from low TB endemic countries, isolates from zoo animals, and isolates obtained in India, both from patients and from veterinarian samples, appeared intermingled in the phylogenetic tree; they were separated by relatively long branches, suggesting a common origin of infection in South Asia (Figure 3). Little is known about the transmission of La3, and the host preferences of this pathogen also remain unclear^{59,79}. The phylogenetic relationships presented here are consistent with direct transmission from cattle-to-cattle in India (Figure 3, cluster A), but they remain inconclusive with respect to direct transmission among and between the other host species. Cattle-to-cattle transmission of La3 inferred through mini-satellite markers (MIRU-VNTR), has been reported previously in Bangladesh⁷⁵. In contrast, no evidence of patient-to-patient transmission has been shown yet, although transmission from one TB patient to cattle has been reported⁷¹, suggesting that humans are not necessarily a dead end for La3. The La3 patient samples analysed here are not well-suited to capture direct transmission given that they mostly represent active TB cases in emigrated patients who most likely have acquired their infection in their country of origin. One exception was the data published by Duffy and colleagues⁵⁹, which was the first to report infection in patients by La3 within the endemic geographic range of this pathogen. Their findings suggest that human infections by La3 are relatively rare when compared to *M. tuberculosis*, given that, of the almost 1,000 patient samples collected in a referral hospital in southern India, only 0.7% belonged to La3. In addition, patients reported to be infected with La3 were often associated with non-pulmonary TB^{59,72}. This is indirect evidence pointing to La3 not being very successful at maintaining infectious cycles in humans, in a way that is reminiscent of zoonotic infections by *M. bovis*, as already suggested by⁵⁹. Future studies will be needed to better understand the host preferences of La3 and how this lineage is transmitted between species. However, given that bTB is endemic in India, which also harbors the largest population of cattle in the world⁸⁰, a plausible scenario is that cattle may play an important role in the dynamics of La3 infections.

Sublineages within La1

Lineage a1 is the most studied member of the animal-adapted MTBC, since bTB has a major economic impact and it is the most common cause of zoonotic TB^{9,81}. In recent years, several studies have compared large collections of WGS of *M. bovis*, bringing new insights into the local transmission dynamics and into the global population structure, phylogeography and evolutionary history of this pathogen^{12–15,56,58}. In a previous study, after an initial compilation of 3,364 genomes representing 35 countries around the world, we defined a reference set of 476 WGS representing the global diversity of *M. bovis* (n=464) and *M. caprae* (n=12)¹². Our results revealed that a large proportion of these genomes belonged to the clonal complex Eu1¹⁶, reflecting biases in sampling and WGS efforts towards the United Kingdom and its former trading partners. Other regions of the world with high *M. bovis* prevalence remained comparatively under-sampled, and yet, we

identified several clades within *M. bovis* that did not belong to either Eu1 or to any of the clonal complexes known at the time¹². Here, we aimed to improve the WGS representation of these previously unclassified clades and to identify new clades by including WGS from countries that were previously under-sampled. After a new search of 5,383 entries on the public domain, following a set of exclusion criteria (seeM), and our own sequencing efforts (19 strains from Turkey, four from Switzerland and two from Italy), we added 221 *M. bovis* and 63 *M. caprae* WGS to the previous identified reference set of 476 WGS¹². In total, we newly analysed 685 La1 and 63 La2 WGS. The phylogenetic reconstruction of the 748 genomes represented in Figure 4 revealed several clades diverging early from the common ancestor of all La1. All these clades were previously identified, and while some formed monophyletic groups corresponding to clonal complexes already defined (Eu1, Eu2, Af1 and Af2), the remaining clades were named transiently as unknown1 to unknown9^{12,15}. In the present analysis, several WGS were added to these identified but unclassified clades, but including more WGS available at NCBI (see methods) did not uncover any new deeply rooted and divergent clades. We therefore considered that the 685 genomes selected here provided a good representation of the global diversity of La1 in its main groups, and could be used to delineate a systematic nomenclature to assist future comparative studies.

Branches that represent early splits from the most recent common ancestor of La1 leading to monophyletic groups represent evolutionary successful populations deriving from common founder events, and thus from a common genetic pool. The strains belonging to these monophyletic groups might share biological properties, which are more similar within than between groups. We have used this rationale to split La1 into several clades, which we hereafter call sublineages in analogy to the human-adapted sublineages of the MTBC. In addition, to increase the operative value of this nomenclature, we have taken into account the geographic distribution of these groups whenever possible, and have attempted to be consistent with the clonal complex nomenclature already in use^{12,14}.

Sublineages La1.1 to La1.3. A sublineage classification was attributed to all well-resolved monophyletic clades showing a strong statistical support and separating early from the most recent common ancestor of La1 (Figure 4 & Figure 5). This was clearly the case for the pyrazinamide-susceptible *M. bovis*¹², the unknown2 group¹² and clonal complex Af2¹⁸. We thus propose to classify these groups as sublineages La1.1, La1.2 and La1.3, respectively (Figure 4 & Figure 5). The shape of the pairwise SNP distances between and among these sublineages also reflects that they have diverged markedly from each other (*Extended data*, Figure 1). Sublineage La1.2 appeared as one of the main genotypes circulating in continental Europe (Figures 4 A & B and Figure 5). This sublineage had been recently called clonal complex European 3 (Eu3)^{27,82}. The WGS we have obtained from cattle in Switzerland and Italy belonged to La1.2 (Figure 4 A), as did a high proportion of genomes isolated from different host species in France²⁶. The BCG group of strains belongs to La1.2, and is closely related

Figure 4. A) Maximum Likelihood topology based on 23,284 polymorphic positions derived from 685 La1 and 63 La2 WGS, after conservatively filtering out several repetitive regions of the genome (see methods). Branch lengths are proportional to nucleotide substitutions and the topology is rooted with one L6 WGS. Support values indicated for the main divisions correspond to bootstrap values. Monophyletic clades corresponding to sublineage divisions are indicated in color as in the legend. Newly sequence La1 in this study are indicated by different symbols as in the legend. **B)** Number of WGS included in the phylogenetic tree per continent (Af = Africa, Am = America, As = Asia, Eu = Europe, Oc = Oceania) and sublineage shown on a square-root scale. The bars are colored according to the sublineage.

Figure 5. A) Schematic illustration of La1 sublineages. The length of the branch is not proportional to genetic distances. Groups without strong bootstrap support (<80) are shown as polytomies. Color codes are the same as in Figure 4. **B)** Geographic distribution of La1 sublineages informed by WGS and *in silico* spoligotype patterns (Extended data: Table 3).

to a veterinarian sample from France, in line with the origin of the BCG vaccine strain in that country⁸³. Several genomes isolated in Ethiopia also belonged to La1.2²⁷, reinforcing the notion that this sublineage has a strong presence in both Western Europe and East-Africa^{12,27}.

Sublineages La1.4 to La1.8. The topology of the phylogenetic tree suggested that the remaining extant groups of La1 were

founded in many instances by very closely related ancestral populations, as shown by the very short internal branches connecting them (Figure 4 A). This could be explained by a history of several migrations occurring more or less simultaneously, followed by rapid diversification in different parts of the world resulting in extant groups with a markedly different geographic distribution (e.g. the clonal complex Af1 and unknown9 groups, the unknown4 and unknown5 groups, and

the unknown6 and unknown7 groups, [Figure 4 A](#) & [Figure 5](#)). Yet, the splits leading to the unknown3, unknown9 and clonal complex Af1 groups are well supported statistically ([Figure 4](#)), and the distributions of their within- and between- pair-wise SNP distances differ markedly (*Extended data*, [Figure 1](#)). Moreover, these groups also occupy different geographic regions ([Figure 5](#)). We therefore propose to classify unknown3, unknown9 and Af1 as sublineages La1.4, La1.5 and La1.6, respectively ([Figure 4](#) & [Figure 5](#)). Most of our isolates from Turkey belonged to La1.4. The geographical distribution of La1.4 based on the WGS and *in silico* spoligotyping suggests a broad distribution spanning Asia, Europe and South America. As for La1.5, the WGS analysed here were isolated from several captive animal species in Germany¹⁵, originally classified as group 09¹⁵, and from humans in Turkey (this study). All these genomes had the spoligotype pattern SB0989, of which we found reports only in the mentioned geographical regions and in Albania^{15,84,85}. As for La1.6, only few WGS were available; however, the work by Muller *et al.*,¹⁹ which provides a very comprehensive description of clonal complex Af1, highlighted the restriction of this group of strains to West-Africa.

The unknown4, clonal complex Eu2 and unknown5 groups form a well-supported monophyletic group. However, the relationships between these groups are unresolved ([Figure 4](#)). Clonal complex Eu2 has diverged from the remaining strains, forming a well-supported monophyletic clade ([Figure 4](#)). The strains classified as unknown4 form quite a diverse group, as indicated by the relatively long branches coalescing to their common ancestor and by the distribution of their within-pair-wise SNP distances ([Figure 4](#) & *Extended data*, [Figure 1](#)). These latter strains were mostly isolated in Brazil¹³, France²⁶ and Germany¹⁵. The modes of the pair-wise SNP distribution of unknown4 and unknown5 suggest, when compared to densely sampled groups like Eu2, that sampling might be incomplete (*Extended data*, [Figure 1](#)). Finally, clonal complex Eu2 and unknown4 occur in Western Europe, America and Southern Africa, overlapping in their geographic distribution and possibly reflecting dispersion events between South America and Western Europe ([Figure 5](#)). As for unknown5, only eight closely related genomes from strains isolated in Zambia were available. All eight genomes have the phylogenetically uninformative spoligotype pattern SB0120, limiting further inferences¹². Based on the above discussed points, we suggest to include clonal complex Eu2, unknown4 and unknown5 in one sublineage, hereafter called La1.7, to further classify clonal complex Eu2 as a subgroup within La1.7 called La1.7.1 and to classify unknown4 and unknown5 as sublineage La1.7.X ([Figure 4](#) & [Figure 5](#)). Further studies with better sampling of the unknown4 and 5 groups are necessary to better understand their population structure.

The remaining genomes classified as clonal complex Eu1, unknown7 and unknown8, and a single genome with an origin in Ethiopia (unknown8)¹², also form a well-supported monophyletic clade. But similarly to the example discussed above, the phylogenetic relationships of their ancestors are not well

resolved. Clonal complex Eu1 and unknown7 each form well-supported monophyletic groups and have distinct geographic distributions. While clonal complex Eu1 has a broad distribution all around the world, strains classified as unknown7 seem much more geographically restricted ([Figure 5](#)). As for unknown6, only seven closely related genomes were available, all corresponding to strains isolated in cervids in the USA⁵⁶. Unknown8 is most closely related to clonal complex Eu1, and as discussed elsewhere^{12,27,86}, probably belongs to a group of strains circulating in Ethiopia. We suggest classifying these groups into one sublineage, La1.8, and to further subdivide clonal complex Eu1 and the group unknown7 into La1.8.1 and La1.8.2, respectively ([Figure 4](#) & [Figure 5](#)). La1.8.1 is among the best characterised groups of strains within *M. bovis*, known to be prevalent in the UK and in regions of the world known to be former UK trading partners. La1.8.2 was mostly composed of WGS from isolates from France²⁶ and a few from Ethiopia²⁷. Similar spoligotypes have been reported in Western- and Southern Europe, suggesting that this might be another common genotype circulating in continental Europe (*Extended data*, [Table 3](#)). In addition, similar spoligotypes have been described in different African countries including Madagascar ([Figure 5](#)). As for unknown6 and 8, we suggest a transient classification as La1.8.X which can be revised once more genomes become available.

Validation of lineage- and sublineage- specific markers using KvarQ

We identified SNPs that are specific to La1, La2 and La3 lineages and La1 sublineages, and which can be used as genotyping markers (see [Methods](#)). To ensure specificity, the resulting list of phylogenetic SNPs obtained from the 839 dataset was compared to a set of polymorphic positions (370,449) obtained from 4,742 WGS representing the genetic diversity of human-adapted lineages L1-L7 and L9³³. After excluding those SNPs, also polymorphic, in at least one out of the 4,742 genomes, 1,959 SNPs remained that were specific for La1, La2, La3 and the described La1 sublineages (*Extended data*, [Table 4](#)). Thereof 87 were selected as phylogenetic markers to create a test suite for KvarQ⁴³ (See [analysis code](#), *Extended data*). KvarQ is a user-friendly, platform-independent tool which allows to scan fastq files for a given list of SNPs, without the need for aligning sequencing reads to a reference genome or *de novo* assemblies⁴³. We validated the test suite with 2,774 WGS from Loiseau *et al.*,¹² not included in our initial 839 dataset and 66 WGS randomly chosen from recently published WGS isolated in Brazil and Algeria⁵²⁻⁵⁴. In parallel, the WGS used to validate KvarQ were aligned with respect to a genome of reference, as indicated in the [Methods](#) and used together with the WGS from the 839 dataset to infer a new phylogenetic tree. According to the KvarQ results (*Extended data*, [Table 5](#)), all WGS belonged to one of the defined La1 sublineages, or to La2, and the visual inspection of the phylogenetic tree indicated that all lineage/sublineage assignments by KvarQ were correct.

Thus, here we provide a specific set of polymorphic positions that can be used to develop molecular assays to classify

strains. In the cases for which WGS exist, sequencing reads can be queried with a new suite of markers (See Zenodo repository), using KvarQ and bypassing the need to run conventional alignment approaches and phylogenetic analysis for strain classification.

Conclusions

In recent years, several thousands of WGS became available for *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*, in particular for the former. Previous phylogenomic studies have unveiled that these pathogens, despite being associated with livestock species, exhibit a broad host species range and marked differences in geographic distribution of different genotypes. Hypothetically, these genotypes might also differ in pathogenicity as in the case of the human-adapted MTBC members. As the number of WGS of livestock-associated MTBC continues to grow in public repositories, there is a need for a practical nomenclature allowing comparative analysis and hypothesis testing. After gathering several thousands of WGS and selecting representatives of different genotypes and geographic regions, we have obtained an exhaustive phylogenetic depiction of *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis* and of the main genetic groups currently known within *M. bovis*. In analogy with the nomenclature in use by the scientific community for the human-adapted members of the MTBC, we proposed here a body of operational nomenclature hierarchically classifying genetic groups within the livestock-associated members in lineages and sublineages. This nomenclature classifies all main genetic groups known currently, and is flexible so as to accommodate new genetic diversity uncovered by new studies. We also provided specific SNPs that can be used to develop molecular assays to identify each of the lineages and sublineages proposed. Furthermore, we developed a new SNP test suite implemented in KvarQ, which allows querying WGS without requiring bioinformatics expertise.

Data availability

Underlying data

European Nucleotide Archive (EBI-EMBL): A new nomenclature for the livestock-associated Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex based on phylogenomics. Accession number: PRJEB46653, <https://identifiers.org/ena.embl:PRJEB46653>

European Nucleotide Archive (EBI-EMBL): Whole Genome sequencing (WGS) of Mycobacterium bovis spoligotype SB0120 and SB0841 isolates circulating in Italy. Accession number PRJEB46575, <https://identifiers.org/ena.embl:PRJEB46575>

Zenodo: A new nomenclature for the livestock-associated Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex based on phylogenomics, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5153095>⁸⁷

This project contains the following underlying data:

- Table 1: Accession numbers and metadata associated with the 839 WGS used of La1, La2 and La3.
- Table 2 - Accession numbers and metadata associated with the 1,226 WGS used as representatives of the whole MTBC.

Extended data

Zenodo: A new nomenclature for the livestock-associated Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex based on phylogenomics, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5153095>⁸⁷

This project contains the following extended data:

- Figure 1: Distribution of the raw pairwise SNP distances between and within main La1 groups.
- Table 3: Spoligotypes patterns inferred from the WGS and used to complement the geographic distribution of La1 sublineages.
- Table 4: Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) specific to livestock-associated MTBC lineages and sublineages. Coordinates based on the *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv annotation (NC_000962.3) are given (Position_ref), and the lineage and or sublineage classification (PhylogeneticSNP). Additionally, the gene-based position is indicated (Position_gene) as well as the kind of mutation based on SnpEff annotation⁴¹. SNPs used to create the new KvarQ testsuite are indicated.
- Table 5: KvarQ results of lineage and sublineage typing done with the new testsuite implemented.

Analysis code available from :

- <https://github.com/gagneux-lab/LivestockAssociated-MTBC/>
- Archived analysis code at time of publication: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5169024>⁸⁸
- License:GNU

Test suite and sublineages implementable in KvarQ⁴³ available from:

- https://github.com/gagneux-lab/LivestockAssociated-MTBC/blob/main/KvarQ_testsuite/MTBC_animals/phylo.py
- Archived analysis code at time of publication: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5169024>⁸⁸
- License: GNU

Acknowledgements

Calculations were performed at sciCORE (<http://scicore.unibas.ch/>) scientific computing core facility at University of Basel. Data were obtained from the TB Portals (<https://tbportals.niaid.nih.gov>), which is an open-access TB data resource supported by the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) Office of Cyber Infrastructure and Computational Biology(OCICB) in Bethesda, MD. These data were collected and submitted by members of the TB Portals Consortium (<https://tbportals.niaid.nih.gov/Partners>) and other data contributors that originally submitted the data to the TB Portals did not participate in the design or analysis of this study.

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Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 13 October 2021

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15117.r27485>

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Liliana C. M. Salvador

Department of Infectious Diseases, College of Veterinary Medicine, University of Georgia, Athens, GA, USA

Summary

Zwyer *et al.* proposed a new nomenclature for three species of the Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex *M. bovis*, *M. orygis* and *M. caprae* by combining phylogenetics with genomics. The goals of their study was to define lineages and sub-lineages based on genetic diversity patterns by analysing a subset of 830 whole genomes extracted from (and representative of) different parts of the world). The authors have found three main lineages La1, La2, and La3, representing respectively, *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*. Within La1, the authors have identified eight sublineages (La1.1-La1.8), which presented distinct geographical patterns (some restricted to an area, while others globally widespread). The authors have also found specific markers (SNPs) to molecularly characterize the different MTBC groups.

General comments

This manuscript is highly relevant for the molecular characterization of MTBC and for future molecular epidemiological and evolutionary studies. There is a large need to extend the current classification system (L1-L7 involving *M. tuberculosis* and *M. africanum*) to other species of the complex and the authors did it using a dataset of 853 genomes from across the world. Overall, I find the manuscript well thought out, very relevant, and timely. I only have a few comments below regarding the analysis performed, which could impact the presented results.

General comments/questions

- Selection of isolates: authors mentioned that they chose 50 genomes per continent. What if the same amount of genomes was taken from an endemic place versus a non-endemic place. How does the local prevalence of the disease affect the genetic diversity that we see in the 50 isolates? Are the 50 genomes enough to characterize well the genetic diversity of a specific place?
- What is MTBC-Livestock associated? How is it defined? Are there any other MTBC species

that infect livestock that are not included? Are there any “MTBC-Livestock associated” lineages that infect the same or even more other types of animals like, for example, badgers or white-tailed deer (both reservoirs for *M. bovis*)?

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: phylogenetics, phylodynamics, bioinformatics, *M. bovis*

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 18 Nov 2021

Daniela Brites, Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute, Basel, Switzerland

We thank the reviewer for her positive feedback.

As for the selection of isolates; the aim of this analysis was to have balanced phylogenetic inference of the total diversity of the MTBC. However, we were not so interested in maximizing genetic diversity within each lineage but rather to have an even representation of endemic and non-endemic places (which we believe to have achieved by sampling randomly each lineage in each continent) at a global scale and show that there is no reason to treat *M. bovis* differently than the human adapted lineages; at least not in what concerns the tree topology. Certainly, as very well pointed out by the reviewer, 50 genomes might not be enough to represent all diversity of *M. bovis* in Africa for instance, but that should be true also for other groups of the MTBC. As to the definition of livestock associated, a similar question was also raised by the other reviewer, revealing that we failed to pass on more

clearly why we consider *M. bovis*, *M. orygis* and *M. caprae* as livestock-associated MTBC members. We have added to the Introduction a few considerations defending this point of view, which we hope addresses the reviewer's concerns.

At the core of considering these species as livestock-associated is the strong evidence that the evolutionary success of *M. bovis*, *M. orygis* and *M. caprae* is associated with the fact that these pathogens are able to cause sustainable infections in livestock species. The fact that these are multi-host pathogens allows them to linger in other animal reservoirs, and in more recent times (post bTB surveillance), this might play a crucial role for these lineages by avoiding local extinctions. However at a global and evolutionary scale, migration and population expansion of *M. bovis* (possibly also *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*, to be confirmed as more data becomes available) are most likely a consequence of cattle husbandry and movements. We think that distinguishes *M. bovis*, *M. orygis* and *M. caprae* from other animal MTBC members, which are also multi-host pathogens (e.g. *M. microti*).

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 16 September 2021

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15117.r27482>

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Lorraine Michelet

Tuberculosis National Reference Laboratory, Laboratory for Animal Health, ANSES, Paris-Est University, Marne-la-Vallée, France

This publication propose a new nomenclature for livestock-associated *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex members, like what exist for human-adapted MTBC. The authors proposed to call the lineages corresponding to *M. bovis*, *M. caprae* and *M. orygis*, respectively La1 to La3 and subdivided La1 (*M. bovis*) into 8 sublineages. This work was necessary in order to facilitate phylogenetic analyzes and to be able to compare studies from different countries.

However, I feel uncomfortable with the use of the term livestock-associated. Indeed, *M. bovis* and *M. caprae* are the main agents responsible for bovine (and caprine) tuberculosis but *M. orygis* is not. If we refer to the OIE Terrestrial Animal Health Code, bovine tuberculosis is caused particularly by *M. bovis* but also by *M. caprae* and, to a lesser extent, by *M. tuberculosis*. I do not understand why the authors include *M. orygis* in the livestock-associated MTBC members. In this case, why do the authors not include *M. microti*, which is known to infect cattle (Jahans et al, 2004) and has recently been identified in several times in goat and cattle.

I can understand that more WGS data are available for *M. orygis* and that allow to better defining this lineage. However, this MTBC member cannot be included as a livestock-associated. Even if few

WGS data are available for *M. microti* and *M. pinnipedii*, I would have expected that the authors include these species as animal-adapted and define two other lineages for these species. The authors could provide some specific markers based on the few available genomes.

In the introduction, I consider that the authors could have more described the previous works done on *M. bovis*, especially on the definition of four clonal complexes. These studies are the result of wide collaborations and have provided a much better understanding of the population structure of *M. bovis* before WGS era. Some other recent works have tried to defined lineages or clusters which are confirmed by this work but the parallel between them is not done. Some references are missing in this part of the introduction (Hauer et al, definition of 9 clusters).

One aspect of the evolution of *M. bovis* is not discussed at all, it is the time. The year of isolation of each sample is an important data that is missing here. The authors suggest further studies on unknown 4, 5, 6 and 8 group to better understand their population structure. However, maybe this could not be done if these lineages have disappeared. For example, all unknown6 samples have been isolated in the 90's except one in 2008. It is well known that selection pressure due to the surveillance and eradication measures put in place in each country has led to a reduction in the genetic diversity of *M. bovis*. This aspect of *M. bovis* evolution could be discussed.

Minor comments

- Page 4 \$ Population structure and genetic distance: add a space between "dataset," and "using the R package".
- Page 7 \$ La2, or *M. caprae*: the authors refer twice to Figure 3 but this should be the Figure 4 (Figure 3 refer to La3 *M. orygis*).
- Page 12 \$ The remaining *M. genomes*: there is a mistake in Spoligotypes.
- Extended table 1: some samples are in duplicate. For example, SRR7851305 rely to G47578 and G49365. Please check carefully your data.

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Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

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Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: microbiology, molecular biology, phylogenetics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 18 Nov 2021

Daniela Brites, Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute, Basel, Switzerland

(Reviewer comments in italics)

This publication propose a new nomenclature for livestock-associated Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex members, like what exist for human-adapted MTBC. The authors proposed to call the lineages corresponding to M. bovis, M. caprae and M. orygis, respectively La1 to La3 and subdivided La1 (M. bovis) into 8 sublineages. This work was necessary in order to facilitate phylogenetic analyzes and to be able to compare studies from different countries.

However, I feel uncomfortable with the use of the term livestock-associated. Indeed, M. bovis and M. caprae are the main agents responsible for bovine (and caprine) tuberculosis but M. orygis is not. If we refer to the OIE Terrestrial Animal Health Code, bovine tuberculosis is caused particularly by M. bovis but also by M. caprae and, to a lesser extent, by M. tuberculosis. I do not understand why the authors include M. orygis in the livestock-associated MTBC members. In this case, why do the authors not include M. microti, which is known to infect cattle (Jahans et al, 2004) and has recently been identified in several times in goat and cattle.

Author Response: We understand the reservations of the reviewer with respect to the livestock-associated terminology, as not much is known about the host range of *M. orygis*. Solid molecular evidence for *M. orygis* infections only started to emerge with whole-genome sequencing relatively recently, and we are in a time where new research about *M. orygis* is defying what we know about bovine TB and zoonotic TB in countries such as India, which has the biggest livestock population in the world and where cattle and humans co-exist very closely. Several recent studies suggest that *M. orygis* is a main cause of zoonotic TB in South Asian countries. That is particularly well demonstrated by the study of Duffy *et al* in India and by a series of other studies reporting infection caused by *M. orygis* in patients of South

Asian origin living in low burden TB countries (cited in our study). There is also direct evidence of *M. orygis* infecting livestock species, and very importantly, transmitting within cattle herds. This is not the case for *M. microti* or *M. tuberculosis*, which can cause TB in livestock species, but are not able to maintain cycles of infection. Transmission of *M. orygis* within cattle is also supported by our genomic analysis. We think that these are enough evidence to consider that livestock species might be one of the reasons for the evolutionary success of *M. orygis* like for *M. bovis* but unlike *M. microti* and *M. tuberculosis*. The reviewer is right when referring to the OIE Terrestrial Animal Health Code and bovine TB. On the human TB side, the WHO has also considered until the latest report in 2020 that zoonotic TB was synonymous of infections by *M. bovis*. We think that reflects the fact that the molecular characterization of the agents of bovine TB in Asia is lagging behind. We have added now more explicitly these considerations to the introduction and thank the reviewer for pointing out that this rationale was not clear in the first version of our manuscript.

I can understand that more WGS data are available for M. orygis and that allow to better defining this lineage. However, this MTBC member cannot be included as a livestock-associated. Even if few WGS data are available for M. microti and M. pinnipedii, I would have expected that the authors include these species as animal-adapted and define two other lineages for these species. The authors could provide some specific markers based on the few available genomes.
Response: We believe that our previous points now demonstrate more clearly why we considered M. orygis as livestock associated. Our interest was to contribute to the molecular characterization of MTBC species that cause a high burden of disease, because they affect some of the most dense animal populations of the world, humans and livestock. We consider this necessary in the light of the growing numbers of WGS available. That is not the case for M. microti and M. pinnipedii. In addition, in this manuscript, we present a rationale for defining lineages based in an interval of SNPs, which is consistent with work that has been previously done for the human-adapted lineages. As shown by us in a previous publication (Brites et al, 2018, Figure 5) M. microti and M. pinnipedii are separated by only 400-500 SNPs, and thus could not be classified as different lineages if we take the same thresholds as for the rest of MTBC complex. Perhaps their split as independent phylogenetic lineages has occurred more recently, or they might have different substitution rates, etc. In any case, we consider that having a better sampling of M. microti and M. pinnipedii is necessary to be able to draw more informed scenarios.

In the introduction, I consider that the authors could have more described the previous works done on M. bovis, especially on the definition of four clonal complexes. These studies are the result of wide collaborations and have provided a much better understanding of the population structure of M. bovis before WGS era. Some other recent works have tried to defined lineages or clusters which are confirmed by this work but the parallel between them is not done. Some references are missing in this part of the introduction (Hauer et al, definition of 9 clusters).

Author Response: Thank you for this comment. We have added these considerations into the introduction. As to the recent works that have tried to define lineages or clusters based on WGS, we think the reviewer refers to Zimpel *et al* 2020 and Hauer *et al* 2019. We have added to Table 1 the correspondence between the groups defined in these two studies and the sub-lineages we are proposing here. We explicitly mention this in the text. "The correspondence between the nomenclature we propose here and previously defined groups based on WGS is given in *Extended data, Table 1*". The study of Hauer *et al* is now

also mentioned in the Introduction and not only in the Results and Discussion section.

One aspect of the evolution of M. bovis is not discussed at all, it is the time. The year of isolation of each sample is an important data that is missing here. The authors suggest further studies on unknown 4, 5, 6 and 8 group to better understand their population structure. However, maybe this could not be done if these lineages have disappeared. For example, all unknown6 samples have been isolated in the 90's except one in 2008. It is well known that selection pressure due to the surveillance and eradication measures put in place in each country has led to a reduction in the genetic diversity of M. bovis. This aspect of M. bovis evolution could be discuss. Response: We agree with the reviewer and have added these points to the end of section Sublineages La1.4 to La1.8.

Minor comments

- *Page 4 \$ Population structure and genetic distance: add a space between "dataset," and "using the R package".*
- *Page 7 \$ La2, or M. caprae: the authors refer twice to Figure 3 but this should be the Figure 4 (Figure 3 refer to La3 M. orygis).*
- *Page 12 \$ The remaining genomes: there is a mistake in Spoligotypes.*
- *Extended table 1: some samples are in duplicate. For example, SRR7851305 rely to G47578 and G49365. Please check carefully*

Author Response: We thank the reviewer for the careful revision. Indeed, we inadvertently downloaded from public databases a few genomes twice. We have removed them from our alignments and redone the analysis and figure 4 and corrected tables 1 and table 2.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
